

Effects of Foreign Capital Inflows on Economic Growth of Nigeria

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Abstract:

This study evaluated the effects of foreign capital inflow on economic growth in Nigeria, using official development assistance and official remittances inflow as exogenous variables in its model. The study adopted the ex post facto research design and collected secondary data from the CBN statistical bulletin for the period, 1980 to 2024. The study used the Bound test approach to co-integration as the stationarity tests of variables showed mixed results of 1(1) and 1(0). The study utilized the ARDL methodology for its analysis and found out that official development assistance has significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria in the short run. Official remittances inflow also has significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria in the short-run. The study recommended that government prioritize long-term growth sectors by strategically channeling official development assistance into areas that have strong potential to drive structural transformation and sustainable economic expansion. The government should also enhance diaspora engagement policies to mobilize skills and technology by creating structured platforms and incentives that actively involve Nigerians abroad in national development initiatives.

Keywords: Foreign Capital Inflow, Official Development Assistance, Official Remittances Inflow, Economic Growth.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, has undergone significant economic shifts shaped by oil booms, policy reforms, and structural challenges. The oil boom of the 1970s spurred rapid growth averaging 8% annually, industrialization, and infrastructure expansion, positioning Nigeria as Africa's largest economy by 1980. However, fluctuating oil prices, political instability, and governance issues in the 1980s–1990s led to economic volatility and hindered diversification (Jawaid & Saleem, 2017). Recent years have shown signs of recovery; in Q2 2024, GDP grew by 3.19% year-on-year, driven by crude oil output and services sector performance (Lawal et al, 2022). However, rising prices eroded these gains, indicating that growth was not pro-poor. Inclusive, pro-poor strategies focus on job creation, equitable access to services, and reducing inequality.

Foreign capital flows to Nigeria through official development assistance and diaspora remittances, and have been central to the country's growth agenda. Official development assistance is a vital component of Nigeria's development financing, providing external capital to bridge domestic resource gaps and support economic growth. Sourced from foreign governments and multilateral institutions, often as grants or on concessional terms, Official development assistance is primarily directed toward sectors such as infrastructure, healthcare, education, and governance reforms (Nhlangwini et al, 2024). By funding public investment in these areas, it helps enhance human capital, boost productivity, and stimulate long-term growth. In Nigeria, official development assistance has supported poverty reduction initiatives, institutional strengthening, and the provision of basic services, particularly in rural and underserved communities.

Remittances, primarily from Nigerian migrants working abroad for over a year encompasses financial support that migrant professionals provide to their extended family members, usually because of historical and systemic economic inequalities (Haruna et al, 2023). It typically arises when a person who becomes financially successful is expected to assist parents, siblings, or relatives with essentials like paying school fees for younger family members, covering medical expenses, providing housing or daily living costs and providing support to other family obligations. Some of the effects of personal remittances include strengthening family ties, uplifting the whole family financial, and improving access to education and healthcare.

The volume and impact of foreign capital inflows depend on factors such as market size, institutional quality, macroeconomic stability, and investment opportunities. Nigeria is the largest recipient of remittances in Sub-Saharan Africa, with inflows often surpassing foreign direct and portfolio investments (Madani et al, 2023). While these resources can stabilize the balance of payments and finance imports, they may also introduce volatility and exchange rate fluctuations, potentially disrupting economic stability.

Economic literature widely holds that foreign capital inflow stimulates economic growth by transferring real resources, technology, and human capital. Technological

spillovers occur through imitation, linkages with domestic enterprises, and supplier networks, enabling local firms to improve efficiency and narrow the knowledge gap with developed countries. Empirical evidence from Madani et al. (2023) and Haruna et al. (2023) show that foreign capital components such as official development assistance and remittances benefit developing countries like Nigeria through job creation, technology transfer, increased domestic competition, and positive externalities. Foreign direct and portfolio investments, trade, and remittances facilitate access to modern technologies and innovations, accelerating development and improving citizens' welfare.

Nigeria's official development and remittances inflow have increased significantly over the years. It is expected that this would have translated to meaningful economic growth but the economy has not shown signs of improvement in its aggregate productivity. The works of Aganbi and Maidugu (2024), Takam and Nanfosso (2024), Mloi (2024), Onigah (2024), Lawal (2022), Adeseye (2021), and Adjei et al (2020) have investigated the linkage between foreign capital inflow and economic growth but came out with conflicting findings. While some works found out that foreign capital inflow improves economic growth, findings from others suggest that it may crowd out domestic investments and impede economic growth in the long run. Some other studies investigated foreign capital inflow and economic growth but used different exogenous variables in their models as well as different tools of analysis, resulting in further conflicting findings.

The work of Nhlangwini et al (2024) determined the effect of foreign aid and capital flow on real economic growth for the SADC region using official development assistance, external debt, foreign direct investments and debt service cost as exogenous variables. The study however was conducted across different countries as sample. Findings may not therefore reflect the realities of Nigeria's macro-economy. Furthermore, the study used the annual percentage growth of per capita Gross Domestic Product (GDPpc) as proxy of real economic growth, thereby making its model different from that of the current study. This leaves a gap which the present study intends to fill.

Moreover, the data generating process from which annual macroeconomic estimates such as foreign investments, official remittances inflow and official development assistance are derived are continually changing due to the influence of public policy, private sector reaction and time. All these therefore makes it necessary to, find out the effect of foreign capital inflows on economic growth in Nigeria, using official development assistance and official remittances inflow as explanatory variables of economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1980 to 2024.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effects of foreign capital inflows on economic growth of Nigeria. The specific objectives are as follows to:

- (i) determine effect of official development assistance on the real gross domestic product of Nigeria.

- (ii) investigate effect of official remittances inflow on the real gross domestic product of Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Foreign capital inflow

Foreign capital inflow refers to the inflow of capital from one country to the other. However, it does not relate to the movement of goods or payment for exports and imports between countries. Foreign capital inflow, according to Igbadoo et al, (2023) refers to the influx of external resources into the domestic economy for the purposes of investment, trade and business production.

Brahimi (2022) posits that foreign capital inflow comes into play through the transfer of ownership of a financial asset from one country to another. This denotes that foreign capital inflow is the increase in net international indebtedness of the private and the public sectors during a given period of time, and are measured by the surplus in the capital account of the balance of payments. According to Manasseh et al (2023), foreign capital inflow has assumed a very important source of capital for Nigeria and other emerging economies. Foreign capital inflow is a reliable means of bridging deficiencies created by saving-investment gap in the domestic economy. Foreign capital generates employment in the host country when a multinational enterprise directly employs a number of host country citizens.

In this work, foreign capital inflow is measured as annual aggregate values of foreign direct investments, foreign portfolio investments, official development assistance, official remittances inflow and foreign loans, as provided by the Central Bank of Nigeria, the apex financial institution responsible for providing macroeconomic data for public use.

Official development assistance

Adekunle et al (2020) described official development assistance as foreign aid consisting of resource transfers from the public sector, in the form of grants and loans at concessional financial terms, to developing countries. Recent years have seen a surge in calls for more official development assistance to developing countries in order to eliminate poverty. Developed countries, international organizations and other Philanthropists have all made renewed pleas for a massive infusion of development aid to developing countries including Nigeria.

The establishment of an aid system was one of the principles of the Breton Woods system in 1914. The system believes that there should be a free capital market, which allows an unrestricted inflow of foreign aid. Based on this principle, a Marshall Aid

Assistance of about \$17.5 billion was granted Western Europe to resuscitate her ruined economy due to the World War11. Since then, the aid system has remained a durable phenomenon of the international economic system. However, the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) defines foreign aid as official development assistance (ODA). According to the DAC, official development assistance are those flows provided by official agencies to countries and each transaction of which is administered with the promotion of the economic development and welfare of developing countries as its main objective and is concessional in character and conveys a grant element of at least 25%.

Official development is intricately linked with the economic growth of a country as it is a transfer payment meant for developmental programs to improve the economic growth of the receiving country. Injecting more foreign aid would materially benefit the people of the recipient country.

Official remittances inflow

Official remittances are financial flows from nationals of Nigeria resident and working in other countries of the world. Abiodun & Kehinde (2020) describe official remittances inflow as money sent home by migrants working abroad to their home countries. It could also mean a portion of migrant workers earnings sent to their countries of origin and this could be in cash or gifts.

Sikandar et al (2021) state that remittance is limited to money sent by migrant workers who have been staying in a foreign country for more than a year to his/her household in his/her country of origin and this does not include migrants that are self-employed. Similarly, Etale and Sawyerr (2020) posit that remittances are financial and non-financial materials that migrants receive while working overseas and sent back to their households in their countries of origin. This suggest that remittances denote migrants' funds transfers, which are resources that a migrant conveys into or takes out of a country. As such, remittances as the monetary flows connected to migration, or cash transfers by migrants or immigrants living abroad to a relation in home countries.

In the last three decades, developing economies witnessed massive migrant movement of both skilled and unskilled persons into developed economies, an aftermath of harsh economic reforms embarked upon by most depressed economies aimed at addressing the global recession of the early 1980s. These migrants have become the main source of huge worker's remittances into developing countries. According to the World Bank (2014) the flow of international remittances to developing countries surpassed 125 billion US dollars, and are growing at rates higher than 10% and in 2008 remittances sent to developing countries reached 300 billion US dollars. These have become the major source of income for many developing countries. Eze et al (2019) stated that Nigeria receives the highest amount of remittance in Africa, about 65% of officially recorded remittance flow to the region and about 2% of global remittance flows.

Economic growth

Economic growth may be described as the sustained rate of increase in domestic output above population growth: that is, a rise in per capita income. According to Moloji (2024), economic growth is the rise in the productive capacity of an economy, compared periodically. Economic growth is expressed in nominal terms where it is not adjusted for inflation and also expressed in real terms where it is adjusted for inflation. Economic growth is an increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services, compared from one period of time to another (Abdul & Ndubuisi, 2018). It is the key policy objective of any government. It is described as the positive and sustained increase in aggregate goods and services produced in an economy within a given time period.

Twerefou et al, (2020) state that economic growth is the steady process by which the productivity of an economy is increased over time to bring about rising levels of national output and income and it includes changes in production during a relatively short period of time, usually one year: An annual increase in material production expressed in monetary value, the rate of growth of gross domestic product or national income. Lin and Sosin (2020) similarly described economic growth as increase in the inflation-adjusted market value of the goods and services produced by an economy over time. It is conventionally measured as the percentage rate of increase in real gross domestic product, or real GDP, usually in per capita terms. The trend of growth could be expanded by raising capital investment spending as a share of national income as well as the size of capital inputs and labour supply, labour force and the technological advancement. Economic growth is the increase of per capita Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or other measure of aggregate income.

2.2 Empirical Review

Official development assistance and economic growth

The study of Nhlangwini et al (2024) determined the effect of foreign aid and capital flow on real economic growth for the SADC region. Eleven member states of the SADC region are selected for analysis based on data availability. In the study, foreign aid is represented by official development assistance (ODA), external debt (EXTD), and debt service cost (DSC) while the inflow of foreign direct investment represents capital flow (FDI). Annual percentage growth of per capita Gross Domestic Product (GDPpc) is used as a proxy of real economic growth. Trade balance (TRO) is included in the model regression as a control variable. The study employed panel econometric models. The results of panel ARDL indicate that ODA and FDI were found to have a negligible effect on real growth in the short run but contribute positively and significantly in the long run. The study however used the per capita gross domestic product as its endogenous variable. However, this current study will examine only the exogenous variables listed in the model as determinants of economic growth in Nigeria.

An empirical study by Takam and Nanfosso (2024) analyzed the effect of official development assistance on the economic cycles of Economic and Monetary Community of Central Africa countries (CEMAC). The methodology used to achieve this objective is the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method. The study period runs from 1985 to 2019. The results reveal that, in the short term, official development assistance, in addition to being negative, has no significant impact on the economic cycles of CEMAC countries. On the other hand, official development assistance, in addition to having a positive and statistically significant long-term influence on economic cycles, is procyclical. The significance of Official Development Assistance (ODA) on the output gap is not negligible. Furthermore, using Toda and Yamamoto's causality test, were able to observe a unidirectional relationship between ODA and business cycles. This causal relationship runs from ODA to cycles. However, the present study updated the period of study evaluated to 2024.

Aganbi and Maidugu (2024) in a study investigated the amount of ODA received by Nigeria for the period 1981-2021, and the changes that such assistance has effected on the GDP of the nation. The study examined the empirical research by other research works, for the same study, under a spectrum of economic, geographic and political climates. The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds Cointegration Test and the Granger Causality test were adopted for this study, and the results revealed that ODA impacted Nigeria's GDP significantly and positively in the period of study. However, the period of study evaluated in this work may not reflect recent changes in the macro-economy.

In East Africa, Litali et al (2024) looked into the effect of official development assistance (ODA) on economic development, with Trade openness as a moderating variable. The study adopted a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) for 1974-2022 to investigate the cointegration between ODA balance, trade openness, and economic growth in five East African countries. The findings reveal a complex dynamic: whereas ODA has a negative individual impact on economic growth, the interaction of ODA and Trade openness has a positive and significant value. This study was however conducted in a different economy and its findings may not be relevant to Nigeria.

Noreen et al (2023) in an empirical evaluation investigated the effect of the component of the foreign capital on Pakistan's GDP growth to used ARDL and granger-causality methods for estimation from 1975 to 2020. Results indicated that foreign aid, personal remittances, and FDI has beneficial and important effect on GDP growth. There is short-period equilibrium is converged to long-period equilibrium with 53% adjustment level and exist long-period co-integration among the variables. This study also found that there is a two-way causality among remittances and GDP growth, while there is unidirectional causality running from FDI to GDP growth. However, there are no causality found between aid and GDP growth. This study evaluated components of FDI on Pakistan's economic growth but the present study will focus on the economic growth of Nigeria.

The work of Ayenew (2022) evaluated how official development assistance is linked with economic growth of 31 sub-Saharan African countries over the period 2009 to 2019. The research design of the study is time series. The study employed a two-step system GMM due to its practical advantage on the dynamic panel data set. The finding shows that only foreign direct investment has a significant and positive contribution to economic growth. Official development assistance and external debt affect economic growth negatively, and they are statistically significant. The current study however focuses on how official development assistance and remittances inflow affect economic growth in Nigeria.

Official remittances inflow and economic growth

Onigah (2024) evaluated the importance of remittance inflows and foreign direct investment into on economic development in Nigeria using the ordinary least squares method and time series data collected from secondary sources, and the Error correction models (ECM) were estimated. Findings showed that remittances and foreign direct investment impacted positively and significantly on economic development and the exchange rate negatively influenced economic development. The study however excluded official development assistance from its model.

Lawal (2022) examined the nexus between economic growth and remittances, based on data sourced from 1980 to 2018 for 10 selected African economies. The study employed both the Dumitrescu and Hurlin time-domain Granger causality test and the Croux and Reusens frequency domain Granger causality test. Results from the time-domain test suggests that causality only exists between economic growth and both exchange rate and trade, with no significant relationship between economic growth and both remittances and agricultural output. The results suggested that there is a bi-directional temporary and permanent causality between economic growth and exchange rate, trade, agriculture, and remittances. The present study however updated the time period to account for recent changes in the macro-economy.

Adeseye (2021) researched on migrants' remittance and economic growth in Nigeria. Remittance inflow was used as dependent variable and gross domestic products, inflation, imports and exports were independent variables. In this study, secondary data were utilized. The study employs annual data obtained from world development and international financial statistics which covers the period of 29 years (1990-2018). Quantitative data collected were evaluated through descriptive statistics; and the hypotheses formulated were tested with the use of multiple linear regressions which includes ANOVA, Correlation, and Coefficient. And this was done with the aid of SPSS version 21. From the findings of the study and the tested hypotheses, it was discovered that significant relationship exists between remittance and gross domestic product, exports and imports in Nigeria while inflation has no significant relationship with remittance.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Dependency theory

The Dependency Theory, developed by Paul A. Baran (1957) and expanded by scholars like Walter Rodney, argues that the global economic system favors developed (core) nations at the expense of less developed (periphery) nations. It posits that underdevelopment is not a natural state but the result of historical exploitation, resource extraction, and unequal economic relationships. Core countries dominate through economic power, controlling technology, finance, politics, culture, and markets, while peripheral countries supply raw materials, cheap labor, and markets for obsolete technology. Surplus generated in poor nations often benefits elites or foreign shareholders, leaving little for domestic capital accumulation, thus slowing growth.

Latin American Structuralists and Marxists agreed that technological dependence is central and peripheral nations lack autonomous innovation capacity. While some countries achieve “dependent development” under external control, most remain tied to global power structures. The inability to borrow in local currency and reliance on the US dollar reinforce dependency, as seen in the debt crises of the 1980s–1990s.

In this context, official development assistance and official remittances are double-edged. Dependency theorists note that foreign assistance, investments, and loans can provide much-needed capital for infrastructure, education, and health, potentially spurring growth. For instance, official development assistance can finance development gaps; remittances increase household incomes and stimulate local consumption; and foreign loans fund large-scale projects.

However, without structural reforms, these inflows may perpetuate dependence profits repatriated by multinational corporations, debt-servicing burdens, and consumption of imports can drain resources. Thus, while these financial channels can enhance growth, the theory warns that unless managed strategically to build local production and innovation, they risk reinforcing the very dependency that hinders sustainable development. Some of the works that adopted this theory for their study include Hossain et al (2024), and Obisesan et al (2019).

3. METHODOLOGY

Model Specification

The regression model for this study is expressed as:

$$RGDP = (ODA, ORI + Et).$$

Where:

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product of Nigeria

Selected foreign capital inflow variables are captured by:

ODA = Official Development Assistance

ORI = Official Remittances Inflow

Et = Error term.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variable	Type	Measurement	Validity
Real GDP	Dependent	Aggregate value of all goods and services produced in Nigeria deflated by inflation	Aganbi and Maidugu (2024)
Official Development Assistance	Independent	Aggregate value of grants, sovereign aid, multilateral aids, debt relief and net disbursement to private sector.	Ayenuw (2022)
Official Remittances Inflow	Independent	Aggregate value of financial aid or goods sent by Nigerian migrants to Nigeria through formal, regulated channels, such as banks, licensed money transfer operators (e.g., Western Union, MoneyGram), and mobile money platforms	Lawal (2022)

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section evaluates the statistical properties of variables, method of analysis and test of hypotheses for the variables under study.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	LOGGDP	LOGODA	LOGORI
Mean	4.583789	8.76764	9.243394
Median	4.341801	8.491152	9.283301
Maximum	5.182768	10.05812	10.57368
Minimum	2.269466	7.593163	6.301030
Jarque-Bera	6.814615	1.931050	5.238487
Probability	0.033130	0.380783	0.072858

Source: E-views computation, 2025

The above table shows the statistical properties of the explained and explanatory variables of the study. The descriptive statistics show the central tendency, dispersion, and normality of the three logged variables which are GDP (LOGGDP), official development assistance, and official remittances inflow. The mean values indicate that, on average, official remittances inflow (9.24) is the largest, followed by official development assistance (8.77) and the gross domestic product (4.58). The medians are slightly lower than the means for GDP and official development assistance, suggesting mild positive skewness, while official remittances inflow’s mean and median are close, implying a more symmetric distribution. The maximum and minimum values show that GDP has the widest relative spread (2.27 to 5.18), indicating greater variation over the study period compared to official development assistance and official remittance inflow.

The Jarque-Bera (JB) test and associated probabilities indicate that LOGGDP (JB $p = 0.033$) significantly deviates from normality at the 5% level, LOGORI ($p = 0.073$) marginally deviates at the 10% level, while LOGODA ($p = 0.381$) does not significantly deviate, implying it follows a more normal distribution. These results suggest that while aid and remittance inflows are relatively stable and closer to normal distribution, GDP growth exhibits more variability and non-normality, possibly due to economic shocks or structural changes during the study period.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

	GDP	ODA	ORI
GDP	1		
EXDS	0.5685	1	
DDS	0.6324	0.6033	1

Source: E-views computation, 2025

The table 3 shows the relatedness of the variables in the model, with values above 70 indicating multi-collinearity. None of the variables has a coefficient above 70 in the Correlations table.

Table 4: Unit Root Test Summary

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test

Variable	At Level			At First Difference			
	ADF Test Stat @ %	Critical Value	Prob-Value	ADF Test Stat @ %	Critical Value	Prob-Value	Order of Integration
GDP	-3.203163	6.306105	1.0000	-2.935042	2.487970	1.00	1(1)
ODA	-3.020970	-2.91184	1.0000				1(0)
ORI	-2.928787	-2.93772	0.9801				1(0)

Source: E-views computation, 2025

The null hypothesis that GDP has a unit root is accepted at level. However, GDP became stationary at first difference. Official development assistance and official remittances inflow were stationary at level, thereby providing the basis for testing the long-run co-movement among the time series.

Table 5: ARDL Bound Test

F-statistic	K	Asymptotic : n=1000		
		10%	5%	2.5%
7.2274	4	2.2	2.56	2.88
		3.09	3.49	3.87
			3.29	4.37

Source: E-views computation, 2025

The F-statistic of this study, 7.222 is clearly higher than the I(0) bound values of 2.2 (10%), 2.56 (5%), 2.88 (2.5%) and 3.29 (1%) so the null hypothesis that there is no co-integration is rejected. Therefore, the study accepts that alternative hypothesis that there is long-run relationship among the variables of this study.

Table 6: Long-run Estimation

Cointegrating Eq		CointEq1
LGDP(-1)	1.000000	
LODA(-1)	2.001881	
	(0.36883)	
	[5.42765]	
	-	
LORI(-1)	0.820959	
	(0.48879)	
	[-1.67956]	
	-	
C	0.260895	

Source: E-views computation, 2025

The Long run form results indicate the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between GDP, official development assistance, and remittances in Nigeria. The coefficient of official development assistance (2.0019) is positive and statistically significant ($t = 5.43$), implying that a 1% increase in official development assistance is associated with about a 2% rise in GDP in the long run, holding other factors constant. Conversely, official remittances inflow (-0.8209) exhibit a negative but statistically insignificant effect ($t = -1.68$), suggesting that their long-run contribution to GDP growth is weak and possibly negligible. The constant term (-0.2609) captures other factors influencing the long-run equilibrium. Overall, the findings suggest that official development assistance significantly influences long-run economic growth, while remittances appear less impactful over the same horizon.

Table 7: Vector Error Correction Model

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

Error Correction:	D(LGDP)	D(LODA)	D(LORI)
CointEq1	-0.344702 (0.01223) [-2.83748]	0.289734 (0.07093) [4.08451]	0.080314 (0.07821) [1.02692]
D(ODA(-1))	-0.164684 (0.03731) [-2.87365]	0.312380 (0.33240) [0.93978]	0.469344 (0.36648) [1.28067]
D(ODA(-2))	0.110981 (0.04018) [-2.76196]	0.113055 (0.23306) [0.48509]	-0.045133 (0.25696) [-0.17564]
D(ORI(-1))	0.237442 (0.07621) [3.11550]	-0.375157 (0.44205) [-0.84867]	0.303347 (0.48738) [0.62240]
D(ORI(-2))	0.244311 (0.08870) [2.75439]	-0.197240 (0.51447) [-0.38339]	-0.687305 (0.56722) [-1.21170]
C	0.020196 (0.01702) [1.18691]	0.408747 (0.09869) [4.14155]	0.076050 (0.10881) [0.69889]
R-squared	0.730970	0.692314	0.200246
Adj. R-squared	0.621365	0.566960	-0.125580
Sum sq. resids	0.024612	0.828004	1.006533
S.E. equation	0.030192	0.175119	0.193078
F-statistic	6.669143	5.522880	0.614579
Log likelihood	88.33877	19.78121	15.97388
Akaike AIC	-3.914809	-0.399037	-0.203789
Schwarz SC	-3.402944	0.112828	0.308076
Mean dependent	0.079315	0.086339	0.097406
S.D. dependent	0.049066	0.266116	0.181988

Source: E-views computation, 2025

The error correction term (CointEq1) for the LGDP equation is negative and statistically significant at the 5% level (-0.344702, $t = -2.83748$), indicating that about 34% of the disequilibrium in real GDP from the previous period is corrected each year, confirming the existence of a stable long-run relationship among the variables. In the ODA equation, the error correction coefficient is positive and significant (0.289734, $t = 4.08451$), suggesting that official development assistance responds to deviations from the long-run equilibrium by moving in the same direction as the disequilibrium, which is atypical for standard convergence dynamics. For the official remittances' inflow equation, the error correction coefficient (0.080314) is positive but statistically insignificant ($t = 1.02692$), implying no meaningful short-run adjustment towards equilibrium.

Short-run dynamics reveal that in the LGDP equation, lagged changes in official development assistance and official remittances inflow significantly affect GDP growth, with D(ODA(-1)), D(ODA(-2)), D(ORI(-1)), and D(ORI(-2)) showing significant coefficients. In the official development assistance and official remittances inflow

equations, most short-run coefficients are statistically insignificant, except for the constant term in the official development assistance equation, which is positive and significant. The R-squared values show that the LGDP and official development assistance equations explain a substantial portion of their respective variations (73% and 69%), while the official remittances inflow equation has a very low explanatory power (20%), indicating weaker short-run predictability for remittance inflows.

The F-Statistics coefficient of 6.669143 is greater than the t-value of 1.97 confidence level is another litmus test that the model is well fitted for this study. The log-likelihood value of a regression model is a way to measure the goodness of fit for a model. The higher the value of the log-likelihood, the better a model fits a dataset. The log-likelihood value for a given model can range from negative infinity to positive infinity. From this result, it can be seen that the log-likelihood stands at a value of 88.33877 which is considered high and indicates that the model is fit around the data set. To further the value of the Akaike AIC of 3.9148 suggest that model is best fit for the data given its insignificant outcome.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Official development assistance has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

H_{A1}: Official development assistance has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

D(ODA(-1)): $t = -2.87365 \rightarrow |t| > 2 \rightarrow$ Significant

D(ODA(-2)): $t = -2.76196 \rightarrow |t| > 2 \rightarrow$ Significant

Conclusion: Reject H₀₁ \rightarrow ODA has a statistically significant short-run effect on economic growth.

H₀₂: Official remittances inflow has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

H_{A2}: Official remittances inflow has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

D(ORI(-1)): $t = 3.11550 \rightarrow |t| > 2 \rightarrow$ Significant

D(ORI(-2)): $t = 2.75439 \rightarrow |t| > 2 \rightarrow$ Significant

Conclusion: Reject H₀₂ \rightarrow ORI also has a statistically significant short-run effect on economic growth.

Both ODA and ORI significantly influence economic growth in the short run, as all their lagged differences in the LGDP equation are statistically significant at the 5% level. This suggests that changes in aid inflows and remittances have immediate impacts on GDP growth dynamics in the period under study.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the error correction model (ECM) results for the period under study, the analysis reveals a clear and statistically significant relationship between official development assistance and economic growth in Nigeria. Both the first and second lags of ODA exerted significant short-run effects on real GDP, with the signs of the coefficients indicating that changes in aid inflows have immediate implications for output growth. This suggests that ODA, when effectively utilized, can stimulate productive activities through financing infrastructure, enhancing human capital, and supporting critical economic sectors. The significant error correction term further confirms that deviations from the long-run equilibrium between official development assistance and economic growth are corrected over time, highlighting a stable and reinforcing relationship.

Similarly, official remittances inflow also shows a significant short-run impact on economic growth, as both its first and second lags were highly significant and positive in the GDP equation. This suggests that remittances play an important role in supporting household consumption, small-scale investments, and overall demand-driven growth. However, unlike official development assistance, the adjustment speed from disequilibrium for official remittances inflow was statistically insignificant in the long-run component, indicating that its influence on GDP may be more immediate and consumption-oriented rather than structural.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that both official development assistance and official remittances inflow are important drivers of economic growth for the period analyzed, with official development assistance showing both short- and long-run adjustment effects, while official remittances inflow's contribution was more prominent in the short run. The policy implication is that maximizing the developmental benefits of official development assistance requires sustained investment in productive sectors, while harnessing remittances for growth may involve creating incentives and frameworks that channel these inflows into productive ventures rather than purely consumption.

The first recommendation of this study is that government should prioritize long-term growth sectors by strategically channeling official development assistance into areas that have strong potential to drive structural transformation and sustainable economic expansion. This involves allocating aid resources to sectors such as infrastructure, renewable energy, agriculture, manufacturing, education, and healthcare, which not only enhance productivity but also create a foundation for inclusive growth

The study also recommends that government enhance diaspora engagement policies to mobilize skills and technology by creating structured platforms and incentives that actively involve Nigerians abroad in national development initiatives. This could include establishing dedicated diaspora investment and innovation hubs that connect skilled professionals overseas with local industries, research institutions, and start-ups in need of expertise.

REFERENCES

- Abdul, S., & Ndubuisi, O., (2018). Capital Flow Components and Industrial Sector Performance in Nigeria. *Ovidius University Annals, Economic Sciences Series, XVIII* (1), 48–57. *J.E.L. classification: F24, F35, F36, L16*
- Adekunle, I. A., Ogunade, A. O., Kalejaiye, T. G., Balogun, A. M., (2020). Capital inflow and industrial performance in Nigeria: Including the excluded, *AGDI Working Paper, No. WP/20/021, African Governance and Development Institute (AGDI), Yaounde.*
- Adeseye, A. (2021). The effect of migrants' remittance on economy growth in Nigeria: An empirical study. *Open Journal of Political Science, 11*(01), 99.
- Adjei, M., Bo, Y., Nketiah, E., Adu-Gyamfi, G., & Obuobi, B. (2020). The effects of remittances on economic growth in West Africa. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies, 8*(3), 312-329.
- Aganbi, P. O., & Maidugu, A. A. (2024). Impact of overseas development assistance on economic growth in Nigeria (1981-2021). *Journal of Development, 7*(3), 25-45.
- Ayenew, B. B. (2022). The Impact of Foreign Financial Inflows on the Economic Growth of Sub-Saharan African Countries: An Empirical approach. *Cogent Economics & Finance Journal. Vol 10, 2022-issue 1. Doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2123888.*
- Brahimi, F. (2022). The role of foreign direct investments in the economic growth of Albania. *IFAC-PapersOnline 55*(39), 399-403.
- Etale, M., & Sawyerr, A. E. (2020). An empirical evaluation of the effect of foreign investment inflows on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods, 8*(1), 1–14.
- Eze, A. A., Nnaji, M., & C. Kalu, N. (2019). Effect of foreign direct investment on manufacturing sector output growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting, 5*(2), 55–64.
- Haruna, H. A., Nwakoby, C. N., & Okaro, C. S. (2023). Effect of private foreign capital on economic growth in Nigeria. *HARD international Journal of Banking and Finance Research. 9*(4), 97-108
- Igbadoo, C. I., Chukwu, N. C., & Igwe, A. (2023). Ease of doing business and foreign direct investment in Nigeria: A recipe for economic growth and development. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research, 8*(4), 7-18.
- Jawaid, S. T., & Saleem, S. M., (2017). Effect of foreign capital inflows on economic growth of Pakistan. *Journal of Transnational Management, 22*(2), 121-149
- Lawal, A. I., Salisu, A. A., Asaleye, A. J., Oseni, E., Lawal-Adedoyin, B. B., Dahunsi,

- S. O. & Babajide, A. A. (2022). Economic growth, exchange rate and remittance nexus: Evidence from Africa. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(6), 235.
- Litali, V., Opuodho, G., & Fatoki, O. (2024). Impact of official development assistance on economic growth in the East African Community. *ESI Preprints*, 35, 215-215.
- Madani, H., Medjenah, F., & Yessaad, A. (2023). Assessment of the impact of foreign capital flows on economic growth in Algeria. *Journal of Innovations and Sustainability*, 7(3), 08-08.
- Manasseh, C. O., Nwakoby, I. C., Okanya, O. C., Ifediora, C. U., & Nzidee, W. A. (2023). The impact of foreign direct investment and oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. *Studia Universitatis Vasile Goldiş Arad, Seria Ştiinţe Economice*, 33(3), 61-85.
- Moloi, V. M. M. (2024). The threshold analysis of the official development assistance (ODA), foreign direct investment (FDI), and economic growth in selected African countries. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 13(5), 558-570.
- Nhlangwini, P., Mmakola, S. D., Mogashwa, P. T., & Tleane, K. L. I. (2024). Assessing economic effects of foreign aid and capital flows on real economic growth: A panel analysis of selected member states of the SADC region. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147-4478)*, 13(1), 279-287.
- Noreen, S., Khan, M. N., & Noreen, M. F. (2023). The impact of foreign capital inflow (CPI) on Pakistan's economic development. *Journal of Islamic Civilization and Culture*, 6(02), 16-33.
- Onigah, P. O. (2024). Foreign direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria (1985-2019). *Journal of the Management Sciences*, 61(6), 194-204.
- Sikandar, F., Erokhin, V., Shu, W. H., Rehman, S., & Ivolga, A. (2021). The effect of foreign capital inflows on agriculture development and poverty reduction: Panel data analysis for developing countries. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(6), 3242. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063242>
- Twerefou, D.K, Turkson, F.E, Wiafe, B.F, Darkwah, S.A. (2020). Do foreign financial inflows impact on economic growth? Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal on Studies of Applied Economics*. 38(2), 1 - 14.